

TikTok Trends: Influence to the Communication Culture of Generation Z

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Abstract

This paper sought to discover and understand the Influence of TikTok Trends to the Communication Culture of Generation Z in terms of how these trends influence their communication, their perception of a generational communication gap, and their ability to maintain professional tones in formal contexts in. The study utilized a descriptive research design, and gathered data from 100 students from Saint Mary's University through an original questionnaire that was validated and tested for reliability. The study found that trends that appeal to the Gen Z's humor, are more likely to manifest in the communication culture of Generation Z, and that they are more inclined to manifest these trends in their communication as a form of self-expression, and as a means to form bonds and connections. The study also found that Gen Z perceive that there is an existing generational communication barrier between them and the older generation. The Gen Z perceive themselves to be able to maintain professional tones in formal spaces, although they manifest the influences of TikTok Trends in academic spaces when they deem it necessary and appropriate. Lastly, collaborative efforts, such as forums may foster better understanding of Gen Z and older generations' communication cultures and proposed academic interventions may create a healthier communication environment in the academe.

Keywords: TikTok Trends, Generation Z, Communication Culture, Communication Barrier

Introduction

TikTok plays a major role in shaping the language of Generation Z by introducing new slang and reviving phrases from earlier platforms. Researchers have observed that TikTok's short-form video format encourages creativity and brevity, which helps spread new linguistic trends quickly. This supports findings that digital platforms are central to language innovation, as users continually adapt their communication to match platform-specific norms and expectations. As a result, TikTok influences not only online interactions but also the way young people communicate in everyday life.

Generation Z is one of the most active groups of social media users worldwide, spending significant time on platforms like TikTok. These platforms serve as important spaces for communication, identity formation, and cultural expression. Gen Z uses them to connect with peers, interact with public figures, and share political and social views. Therefore, understanding how social media affects the communication patterns of Generation Z is key to recognizing its broader impact on their lives.

As Generation Z adopts a communication culture that roots from TikTok trends, this research aims to study the implications of these new behaviors. It is also this study's objective to recommend an intervention plan for a better communication context that will allow Gen Z and the other generations to adapt to each other and form an effective and healthy communication space.

This study finds its basis on two of the essential courses in the communication field, Social Media Principles and Practices and Communication, Culture and Society. The former highlights the structure, functionality and influence of social media platforms, offering possible tools for trends analysis found on TikTok. The latter explores how communication technologies influence cultural norms and societal behaviors.

The blending of these two courses gives a firm academic foundation for this study, with the assurance that it is not limited to the technical dynamics only but also critically analyzes its wider cultural and societal concerns. This interaction emphasizes the essential aspect of interdisciplinary methods in addressing complex digital phenomena in modern communication studies.

While there have been many studies affirming the influence of TikTok on the communication behaviors of Generation Z, there are no existing studies that specifically delve into the influences of trends, and how they influence the different contexts of communication in the lives of Generation Z. Because of this, there are also limited sources that seek intervention plans to address the implications of these trends in aspects of the communication environment of Generation Z where there might be negative effects of these influences.

Moreover, the concept of communication culture has been highlighted in academic spaces as usually behaviors learned in individuals' ethnicity, religion, and family background. There is yet to be a study that links this concept in light of an individual's generation. Hence, this research aims to understand communication culture in this light.

Additionally, Generation Z will be the majority, if not the entirety, of university students in the next thirteen years. Therefore, there is an underlying importance to understanding their communication culture for a better communication environment in the academe.

Objectives of the Study

This study aims to discover and understand the implications of TikTok to the communication culture of Generation Z by the end of May 2025 by answering the following queries:

1. Which TikTok trends impact the communication culture of Generation Z?
2. How do TikTok trends manifest on Gen Z's Communication Culture?
3. Do TikTok trends create a communication barrier between Gen Z and the older generations as perceived by Gen Z?
4. How do TikTok trends impact Gen Z's ability to maintain professional tones in written and verbal conversation?
5. What intervention plan can be done to promote a better communication culture of Gen Z?

Methodology

The study followed a qualitative-descriptive approach. Its goal was to explore, describe, and understand how TikTok trends were manifested in the communication culture of Generation Z. It focused on the impact of current TikTok trends on the respondents' communication with others and their daily lives. This method allowed the researchers to gather insights on how frequently TikTok trends manifested among the respondents and to explain their tendencies and effects.

The study was conducted at Saint Mary's University in Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, targeting Generation Z respondents from the university. The data-gathering procedure involved the use of physical questionnaires, which were distributed directly to the selected Generation Z participants.

This approach was deemed practical and relevant, as it allowed the researchers to focus on a specific population within the academic community.

The questionnaire composed of a checklist, Likert Scales, and open ended questions to gather data on the influence of TikTok trends to the Communication Culture of Generation Z.

The respondents of the study were composed of 100 Generation Z individuals studying at Saint Mary's University, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya, selected through stratified random sampling. Twenty-five students from each of the schools within Saint Mary's University were chosen to ensure equal distribution of the sample size. The desired sample size was also based on the Central Limit Theorem, which states that the population is normally distributed when the sample size is greater than or equal to 30.

The respondents consisted of Generation Z students at Saint Mary's University who were born between the years 1997 and 2012. They were required to have a TikTok account and actively watch TikTok content.

Data collection took place in early May 2025. Researchers obtained approval from deans of four academic schools and coordinated with faculty to gather data from selected classes. From each school, 30 eligible students were randomly chosen, though only 25 were needed, with extras selected as backups. Participation was voluntary, supported by informed consent, and students could withdraw at any time. Data was gathered following a consistent procedure, then analyzed and interpreted to support the study's findings.

Results and Discussion

Section 1. TikTok Trends that Manifest in the Communication Culture of Generation Z

Table 1

TikTok Terminologies that Impact the Communication Culture of Gen Z

These results suggest that TikTok Terminologies with the most significant impact are those that describe people and situations in a humorous, teasing way. These findings imply that Generation Z tend to engage with language that is playful, informal, and socially driven. The findings suggest that such terminologies allow them to quickly communicate shared attitudes or judgments in a way that is entertaining and easily understood within their online communities.

TikTok Terminologies	STEH(<i>f</i>)	%	SHANS(<i>f</i>)	%	SEAIT(<i>f</i>)	%	SAB (<i>f</i>)	%	Total <i>f</i>	%
Golden Retriever Energy	8	32%	8	32%	11	44%	16	64%	43	43%
Yap	10	40%	9	36%	13	52%	13	52%	45	45%
Aesthetic	18	72%	16	64%	21	84%	19	76%	74	74%
Rizz	12	48%	13	52%	14	56%	16	64%	55	55%
Ekalal, Eabab	11	44%	17	68%	14	56%	18	72%	60	60%
"_" Core	16	64%	17	68%	13	52%	16	64%	62	62%
Cloutchaser	15	60%	15	60%	12	48%	16	64%	58	58%
Coquette	9	36%	11	44%	10	40%	16	64%	46	46%
Delulu	14	56%	18	72%	19	76%	21	84%	72	72%
Simp	13	52%	12	48%	13	52%	12	48%	50	50%
Tea	14	56%	17	68%	14	56%	13	52%	58	58%
Dogshow	17	68%	18	72%	16	64%	19	76%	70	70%
Nonchalant	19	76%	12	48%	18	72%	19	76%	68	68%

Table 2*TikTok Music and Sound that Impact the Communication Culture of Gen Z*

The findings indicate the Generation Z generally gravitate towards TikTok audio that express their emotions, like concern, confusion, and encouragement, in an exaggerated humorous way. This implies that emotional expression among Generation Z is often mediated through humorous and exaggerated audio content on TikTok. This suggests a communicative pattern in which complex emotional emotions are externalized in a performative manner.

TikTok Music and Sound	STEH(<i>f</i>)	%	SHANS(<i>f</i>)	%	SEAIT(<i>f</i>)	%	SAB(<i>f</i>)	%	Total <i>f</i>	%
Wait, let me love you like I love you	10	40%	8	32%	14	56%	8	32%	40	40%
Put your hand on your hip, when you dip, I dip, we dip	8	32%	5	20%	8	32%	9	36%	30	30%
Success ka eh, bigla kang sumuccess eh	15	60%	19	76%	16	64%	21	84%	71	71%
Ayan, si ate ko, naglalaro na naman siya ng ganda-gandahan	13	52%	11	44%	10	40%	16	64%	50	50%
Nandito tayo sa fine dining restaurant	13	52%	13	52%	13	52%	19	76%	58	58%
Prosti, call girl, kalapating mababa ang lipad	12	48%	11	44%	6	24%	11	44%	40	40%
Eh? Eh? Ehh? Ehh? Ehhhhh?	18	72%	13	52%	18	72%	20	80%	69	69%
Bidyohi ko! You are not allow! Saksi mo? Mapriso ka!	7	28%	4	16%	11	44%	10	40%	32	32%
Listen look and listen and learn	12	48%	10	40%	18	72%	15	60%	55	55%
esophagus esophagus habang tayo ay kumakain sa hapag kainan...	8	32%	5	20%	14	56%	20	80%	47	47%
In the klerb, we all fam	10	40%	7	28%	7	28%	8	32%	32	32%
Magiging kwento ka talaga, ang bait mong bata ka	14	56%	18	72%	20	80%	18	72%	70	70%

Table 3*TikTok Expressions and Mannerisms that Impact the Communication Culture of Gen Z*

The TikTok Mannerisms and Expressions with the greatest influence to the communication culture of Generation Z are one-to-two-syllable words or vocalizations that allow the speaker to encapsulate complex thoughts in a simple yet expressive manner.

These findings imply that the communication preferences of Generation Z are shifting toward more efficient forms of expression. The use of one-to-two-syllable words or vocalizations indicates a trend toward linguistic minimalism, where meaning is conveyed through brevity and tone rather than detailed verbal elaboration. This suggests that in both digital and interpersonal contexts, communicative efficiency and emotional resonance are prioritized.

TikTok Expressions and Mannerisms	STEH(<i>f</i>)	%	SHANS(<i>f</i>)	%	SEAIT(<i>f</i>)	%	SAB (<i>f</i>)	%	<i>Total f</i>	%
Finger Clap	9	36%	8	32%	4	16%	8	32%	29	29%
Give me my money	7	28%	10	40%	14	56%	17	68%	48	48%
Repeating words in a high-pitched exaggerated tone (keratin, KERATIN?!)	16	64%	11	44%	11	44%	17	68%	55	55%
Slay	16	64%	21	84%	16	64%	19	76%	72	72%
Dasurv	17	68%	21	84%	18	72%	18	72%	74	74%
Sheesh	16	64%	17	68%	24	96%	18	72%	75	75%
Huuuy!	19	76%	12	48%	13	52%	17	68%	61	61%
Sashay away, Shantay you stay	9	36%	2	8%	7	28%	6	24%	24	24%
Boogsh	17	68%	12	48%	9	36%	13	52%	51	51%
Lavarn	14	56%	13	52%	10	40%	11	44%	48	48%

Table 4*TikTok Words and Phrases that Impact the Communication Culture of Gen Z*

The most impactful TikTok words and phrases are reactions to other people's behaviors, actions, or appearance that are applicable in more than one context or situation. It shows that the communication culture of Generation Z thrives on the application of these trends to express their approval and disapproval in a creative, nonconventional way.

These findings imply that the most impactful TikTok words and phrases are those that serve as flexible reactions to various situations. Their broad applicability across different contexts suggests that Gen Z values language that can be reused in multiple social situations. This indicates a communication style among Generation Z that favors adaptable, trend-based expressions for signaling approval or disapproval. The use of such language may support the development of a shared digital vocabulary, allowing for efficient and creative social interaction within online communities.

TikTok Words and Phrases	STEH(<i>f</i>)	%	SHANS(<i>f</i>)	%	SEAIT(<i>f</i>)	%	SAB (<i>f</i>)	%	<i>Total f</i>	%
Suspek suspek	18	72%	13	52%	17	68%	18	72%	66	66%
Very demure, very mindful	17	68%	20	80%	14	56%	22	88%	73	73%
Thank you, Beyonce	16	64%	12	48%	7	28%	15	60%	50	50%
We listen and we don't judge	16	64%	17	68%	17	68%	22	88%	72	72%
Fit check	15	60%	16	64%	16	64%	21	84%	68	68%
In my " _ " era	16	64%	16	64%	11	44%	17	68%	60	60%
Ate and left no crumbs	11	44%	9	36%	8	32%	11	44%	39	39%
In the clurb, we all fam	12	48%	11	44%	7	28%	7	28%	37	37%
It's giving	17	68%	18	72%	14	56%	23	92%	72	72%
A day in a life as " _ "	13	52%	12	48%	16	64%	19	76%	60	60%
Main Character	17	68%	15	60%	13	52%	18	72%	63	63%
Forda...	15	60%	15	60%	13	52%	20	80%	63	63%
Queen never cry	8	32%	5	20%	8	32%	9	36%	30	30%
Match my freak	4	16%	6	24%	5	20%	8	32%	23	23%

Themes

Self-Expression

A consensus from more than half of the total number of participants reported that TikTok Trends that assist their expression of opinions, feelings, and reactions greatly impact their daily interactions. STEH P1 stated that they use *“Mostly TikTok Terminologies I get from trending content creators like “it’s giving”, “fit check”, and others”*, while SAB P24 indicates: *“I find TikTok expressions like “slay” “sheesh” and “dasurv” in my daily interactions with my friend(s). Those expressions are found in our conversation(s).”* These accounts from the research respondents indicate the clear manifestation of TikTok Trends that encourage creative short quips to empower self-expression among the Generation Z.

Entertainment

Many of the students indicated that they find themselves using amusing and emotion-provoking trends. SEAIT P11 incorporates *“Funny memes, anime, quotes”* in their communication culture, while SAB P13 utilizes *“memes, relapse vids, animals’ core, Hev Abi”* the most. Interestingly, the word *“brainrot”*, which refers to humorous but senseless TikTok content, also appeared in respondents’ responses several times. Examples are the responses: *“Italian brainrot, POV’s”* of STEH P22, *“Those brainrots vids and mostly “Filipino Core”* from SEAIT P4, and *“Occasionally, western brainrot”* from SAB P1. These manifestations tell us that Gen Z enjoy including vocabulary that may be deemed as silly in their communication culture, and that entertainment plays a significant factor in their selection of which trends they choose to impact their communication.

Personal Connection and Relatability

Several respondents also reported utilizing trends that involve content that fosters personal connection and relatability. SAB P3 indicated that the most influential TikTok Trend in their daily are a *“The type of TikTok Trends I find myself using the most is the “a day in my life as” or mini vlog(s)”*. While SAB P16 specified that they mostly manifest TikTok Trends that are *“Business, POV of life”*. In addition, SHANS P3 reported that they utilize trends that involve *“Dark web core, Cats, Business, Thrift Shops”*. This indicates that TikTok trends that culminate shared interests also tend to appear in the Communication Culture of Generation Z.

Section 2. Manifestation of TikTok Trends in the Communication Culture of Generation Z

Table 5

Manifestation of TikTok Trends in the Communication Culture of Generation Z

The findings suggest that TikTok Trends manifest in the respondents’ communication culture in situations where they intend to express their thoughts, feelings and interests. Moreover, it also appeared on indicators that show instances of a sense of community and greater connection through shared experiences, humor, and interests with their peers.

The results also indicate that TikTok Trends rarely manifest in the aspect of Generation Z’s communication culture that deals with serious and unfamiliar situations. The respondents determined that they filter or leave out TikTok trends in their manner of communicating in impersonal interactions with individuals of authority, and strangers.

Indicators	Mean	SD	AD
I express my ideas better in conversations using words, expressions, and gestures I adapted from TikTok Trends.	2.84	0.81	FM
I express my emotions better using words, expressions, and gestures I adapted from TikTok Trends.	2.7	0.89	FM
I have trouble expressing my thoughts when using words, expressions, and gestures I adapted from TikTok Trends.	2.09	0.82	RM
I have trouble expressing my emotions when using words, expressions, and gestures I adapted from TikTok Trends.	2.12	0.90	RM
I resolve conflicts using concepts I learned from TikTok trends.	2.23	0.94	RM
I worsen conflicts when using concepts I learned from TikTok trends.	1.87	0.87	RM
I expect people to respond to me in the same manner when I use tones and slangs that I learned from TikTok.	2.64	0.95	FM
I feel connected better to people when they talk to me using words, expressions, and gestures from TikTok Trends that I recognize.	2.85	0.96	FM
I feel less connected to people when they use words, expressions, and gestures from TikTok Trends that I don't recognize.	2.06	0.84	RM
I often use slang, phrases, expressions, and gestures popularized on TikTok when talking in person with people I have a close personal relationship with.	2.91	0.90	FM
I often use slang, phrases, expressions, and gestures popularized on TikTok when talking in person with people I don't have a close personal relationship with.	2.12	0.92	RM
I often use slang, phrases, expressions, and gestures popularized on TikTok when talking online with people I have a close personal relationship with.	2.92	0.84	FM
I often use slang, phrases, expressions, and gestures popularized on TikTok when talking online with people I don't have a close personal relationship with.	2.06	0.93	RM
I often use slang, phrases, expressions, and gestures popularized on TikTok when posting and commenting on social media platforms.	2.59	0.93	FM
I often use slang, phrases, expressions, and gestures popularized on TikTok in serious academic situations.	1.79	0.90	RM
I often use slang, phrases, expressions, and gestures popularized on TikTok when talking to faculty and staff of the university.	1.56	0.87	RM
TikTok trends shape the way I interact with my peers.	2.55	0.90	FM
I feel more connected with others when we use words, phrases, expressions, tone, or gestures from TikTok trends in our conversations.	2.65	0.96	FM
TikTok has introduced me to new communication styles that I now use frequently.	2.78	0.85	FM
Memes or jokes from TikTok are a major part of my group chats or online communication.	3.07	0.88	FM
In casual conversations, I find myself using words, phrases, expressions, tone, or gestures I adapted from TikTok trends.	2.78	0.90	FM
In formal conversations, I find myself using words, phrases, expressions, tone, or gestures I adapted from TikTok trends.	1.97	1.02	RM
Using references from TikTok helps me build relationships with others in my age group.	2.77	0.92	FM
TikTok trends impact how I communicate in formal settings.	2.07	1.02	RM

Themes

Self-Expression

TikTok trends appear to serve as a way for Gen Z to express their ideas through terminologies, expressions, and mannerisms from TikTok Trends. STEH P13 stated, *"I feel liberated, (e)specially on my freedom of speech"*. SAB P17 also noted how TikTok trends influence their manner of communicating. They shared, *"It affects mostly how I communicate with words. I now use slangs that I learned from TikTok"*

These responses reflect TikTok Trends' capacity to help express Gen ideas in a creative manner that does away with the restrictive nature of standard vocabulary.

Personal Connection and Relatability

This reflects how TikTok Trends influence Gen Z's interactions in terms of fostering a sense of similarity and camaraderie with others. Respondents described how utilizing these trends in their interactions have helped create opportunities to build bonds, and naturally interact with their peers.

STEH P4 shared, *"The gestures, slangs, and phrases I adapted from TikTok makes it somewhat easier for me to communicate with other people"*, while SHANS P19 reported, *"I relate to the usual conversation in my generation"*. SEAIT P3 also explained, *"It helps me to be socially active with my friends and other people because im also a quiet and introverted person"*. Lastly, SEAIT P19 stated, *"It gives me ideas to fit in so that I can be more confident."*

These statements suggest that TikTok trends manifest in Generation Z's communication culture in areas of network building and feeling a sense of belongingness. It can be derived, then, that the respondents feel encouraged to use communication styles, topics, and behaviors based on TikTok Trends because these trends make it easier for them to connect and communicate with their peers.

Information Sharing

Information Sharing highlights that information sharing, such as news-related and academic-related topics, sometimes manifest on the communication culture of respondents. SAB P5 shared, *"It keeps me updated from almost everyt hing such as trends, issues, news, and more"*. This response reflects that TikTok trends manifest influences, not just for entertainment, but for substantial information sharing as well.

Section 3. Presence of Generational Communication Barrier Influenced by Tiktok Trends, as Perceived by Gen Z

Table 6

Influence of TikTok Trends to the Generational Communication Barrier as Perceived by Gen Z

These results collectively suggest that members of Generation Z perceive there is a communication barrier between them and older generations when TikTok references are used, mainly due to their experience with a lack of understanding and unfamiliarity on the part of some of the older individuals. However, despite this barrier, Gen Z do not appear significantly discouraged or frustrated, indicating a degree of adaptability or a selective approach to using such language depending on the audience.

Moreover, the findings reveal that while respondents are aware that some members of the older generations may not grasp TikTok references, Gen Z is still relatively comfortable using them. The effect of using TikTok trends in these conversations, therefore, does not always result in conflict or miscommunication, but it can contribute to a subtle disconnect.

Indicators	Mean	SD	AD
Older generations find it difficult to understand my humor, jokes, or banter based on TikTok trends.	3.08	0.91	FM
Older generations find it difficult to understand when I use TikTok slang in conversations.	3.13	0.90	FM
I often need to explain the TikTok slang that I use to older generations.	3.93	0.90	FM
The older generations find it difficult to relate to my expressions, gestures, and words that I reference from TikTok.	2.98	0.91	FM
The integration of TikTok trends in my casual conversation makes it harder for me to connect with older generations.	2.68	0.86	FM
I avoid having conversation with older generation because they don't get the terms I reference from TikTok.	2.10	0.99	RM
I find myself having to adjust my vocabulary to accommodate the older generations.	2.76	1.03	FM
I find it frustrating to have conversations with older generations because they don't get the terms that I reference from TikTok.	2.09	0.92	RM
I find myself having to explain the TikTok trends I reference in my conversations with older generations.	2.64	0.85	FM
There are times older generations misinterpret my statements when I use TikTok references during conversations.	2.9	0.85	FM
I have been called annoying by older generations for using TikTok words, expressions, and gestures.	2.24	1.04	RM

Themes

Lack of Understanding

The qualitative data revealed recurring patterns that strongly support the quantitative findings of the study, particularly in relation to the communication barrier between generations influenced by TikTok trends.

Under this theme, several participants expressed that some older generations fail to grasp the meaning of TikTok references or slang used by Gen Z. For instance, STEH P1 stated, "*They act clueless,*" while another mentioned, "*They react confused on what we Gen Zs say.*" These statements illustrate a disconnect in language and digital culture exposure, leading to confusion and misunderstandings.

Lack of Interest

This theme reflects Gen Z's perceived passive or indifferent reactions from older generations when exposed to TikTok-related language or references. The participants' insights suggest the idea that unfamiliarity may lead to disengagement during conversations.

One respondent from SHANS P1 shared, *“They don’t know how to respond,”* indicating that older individuals may choose not to engage when they do not understand what is being said. Similarly, a participant from SAB P1 noted, *“No reaction, because they didn’t know what I’m talking about,”* suggesting a lack of response when met with unfamiliar TikTok terms.

These responses suggest that the absence of shared understanding may lead older generations to withdraw from the conversation altogether, contributing further to Gen Z’s perception of the existence of a generational communication gap.

Willingness to Connect

The theme Willingness to Connect reflects the efforts of some older individuals to engage in conversations that involve TikTok references, despite initial confusion. This theme suggests that while there may be a generational gap, there is also a desire among some older people to understand and relate to younger individuals.

A participant from SEAIT P1 shared, *“Confused, then asked some questions,”* indicating that although older individuals may not immediately grasp TikTok-related terms, they show interest by seeking clarification. Similarly, a response from STEH P1 noted, *“Sometimes they want to relate,”* highlighting the openness of some older people to connect.

These responses demonstrate that despite differences in digital exposure with some members of the older generations, they show willingness to learn about the unfamiliar terms and expressions used by Gen Z in their daily interactions.

Uncertain

The theme Uncertain highlights the hesitation and selective communication patterns of participants when engaging with older generations using TikTok references. It reflects both the uncertainty about how such expressions might be interpreted and a mindful effort to prevent possible misunderstandings or unintended disrespect.

One respondent from SAB P1 stated, *“Nothing. I am not using it to the older people,”* indicating a deliberate choice to refrain from using TikTok-related language in intergenerational conversations. Similarly, a participant from SHANS P1 shared, *“I don’t speak with them using words from TikTok because I respect elders.”*

These responses suggest that some members of Gen Z are uncertain about how appropriate or effective it is to incorporate TikTok trends when speaking with older individuals.

Section 4. Impact of TikTok Trends on the Ability of Generation Z to Maintain Professional Tones in Written and Verbal Conversations

Table 7

Influence of TikTok Trends to Written Professional Contexts

These findings indicate that Generation Z is less concerned about maintaining professional tones in message exchanges with people in the same age group, but are most likely to purposely avoid including manifestations of TikTok Trends to their communication style when speaking to higher authority figures in online written platforms.

This indicates that members of Generation Z possess self-awareness in formal written contexts, and are capable of maintaining professional tones in written conversation when they deem it necessary.

Written Professional Contexts				
Indicators	Mean	SD	AR	
I use words, phrases, and/or expressions from TikTok slang on texts or chats with university faculty and staff.	1.67	0.91	RM	
I use words, phrases, and/or expressions from TikTok slang on texts or chats with my classmates/peers.	3.03	0.93	FM	
I use words, phrases, and/or expressions from TikTok slang on formal groupchats with my classmates.	2.26	0.04	FM	
I use TikTok words, phrases, and/or expressions on emails addressed to university faculty and/or staff.	1.44	0.81	NYM	
I use TikTok words, phrases, and/or expressions on emails addressed to my classmates.	2.03	1.04	RM	
I use words, phrases, and/or expressions from TikTok slang on formal school documents.	1.53	0.87	RM	
I use TikTok words, phrases, and/or expressions on formal letters.	1.54	0.85	RM	
I use words, phrases, and/or expressions from TikTok slang on essays required in my classes.	1.82	0.94	RM	
I use words, phrases, and/or expressions from TikTok slang on narrative reports required in my classes.	1.77	0.87	RM	
I use words, phrases, and/or expressions from TikTok slang on powerpoint presentations required in my classes.	2.01	0.90	RM	

Table 11

Influence of TikTok Trends to Verbal Professional Contexts

The results indicate that Generation Z are capable of maintaining professional tones in verbal interactions held in professional settings, as the manifestations of TikTok Trends in their communication culture are rarely observed in the professional setting.

Verbal Professional Contexts				
Indicators	Mean	SD	AR	
I use words, phrases, and/or expressions from TikTok slang on one-on-one conversations with my professors during formal class discussions.	1.47	0.75	NYM	
I use words, phrases, and/or expressions from TikTok slang on one-on-one conversations with my classmates during formal class discussions.	1.67	0.81	RM	
I use words, phrases, and/or expressions from TikTok slang on group conversations with my professors during formal class discussions.	1.49	0.72	NYM	
I use words, phrases, and/or expressions from TikTok slang on group conversations with my classmates during formal class discussions.	1.69	0.84	RM	
I use words, phrases, and/or expressions from TikTok slang during formal class presentations.	1.62	0.78	RM	
I use words, phrases, and/or expressions from TikTok slang during group presentations in class.	1.76	0.88	RM	
I feel that using TikTok slang helps me express myself more authentically in class discussions.	1.91	0.98	RM	
I use TikTok slang when speaking in front of the class.	1.8	0.89	RM	
I use words, phrases, and/or expressions from TikTok slang with a professors during formal discussion settings (ex. class discussion, meeting).	1.51	0.67	RM	
I use words, phrases, and/or expressions from TikTok slang with my peers during formal discussion settings (ex. class discussion, meeting).	1.63	0.76	RM	

Themes

Presence of Manifestations of TikTok Trends in the Communication Culture of Generation Z in Professional Context

Although the quantitative results of the study determined that Generation Z is able to maintain professional tones, qualitative results show that the manifestation of TikTok Trends still extends in formal contexts.

The data suggests that the presence of these manifestations is mostly situation-dependent. STEH P4 stated, *"I use expressions, words, and communication styles from TikTok Trends in academic settings when the situation calls for it."* While STEH P8 said, *"I usually use these things when the topic is light, however, I switch to being formal during formal class discussions. Usually, it depends on the atmosphere of the class."*

Some respondents also admitted to using TikTok-related expressions and jargons when presenting in front of the class to command attention. These manifestations are being used by Generation Z to maintain engagement, rather than to disrespect the context, as they utilize these while keeping in mind their roles as students and presenters.

SAB P12 stated that they utilize communication influences from TikTok *"Usually when I have presentations that can include TikTok slangs, just to ensure that my classmates still listen to me, as long as it's appropriate."*

Absence of Manifestations of TikTok Trends in the Communication Culture of Generation Z in Professional Context

Alternatively, 30% of the respondents maintain that they avoid exhibiting the influence of TikTok Trends when communicating in professional contexts.

STEH P7 report to communicate with influences from TikTok Trends *"In a more conversational setting- like conv(ersations) during vacant time w(ith)(my) advisers"*. SHANS P8 also denies using TikTok language and mannerisms in professional circumstances. They expressed this by saying, *"I don't use expressions, words, and communication styles from TikTok Trends in (the) academic setting."* These statements imply that some members of Generation Z are also set on maintaining professional tones in academic settings in the conventional way.

However, there are also some respondents who do so for fear of how they will be perceived. SEAIT P20 admits, *"I really don't use it in academic settings because I might be called cringe and corny"*. This indicates that Gen Z's perception of their surroundings effectively plays a significant role in ensuring that they maintain professional tones where it is demanded.

Section 5. Intervention Plan to Promote a Better Communication Culture of Gen Z

With the evolving landscape of communication shaped by digital media such as TikTok, it is important to equip Gen Z with enough information necessary to help maneuver their communication culture to appropriately adapt based on the environment effectively and responsibly. To address the gaps based on the findings, the researchers developed intervention plans to improve the communication of Generation Z.

For the Communication Barrier between Gen Z and the Older Generations

1. Conduct an open forum – workshop for students, teachers, and parents where each other’s communication culture is discussed, and a compromise on the preferred manner of communicating is made.
2. Document the consensus from the open forum-workshop
3. Videos to spread awareness on digital literacy and appropriate communication practices.
4. Disseminate videos through TikTok and Facebook.

For the Academe

1. Conduct an in-depth research of the faculty’s perspective and experiences with the manifestations of the TikTok Trends in the classroom.
2. Use the findings to adjust teaching styles based on the results.
3. Conduct seminars, open forums, and workshops to determine a middle ground where the dignity of academic contexts is maintained while maintaining students access to freedom of expression.
4. Adapt general courses that assist students in applying traditionally appropriate communication behaviors in formal contexts. (Business Correspondence, Purposive Communication)

Conclusions

1. TikTok Trends with content that encourage self-expression, provide entertainment, and build personal connection and relatability are most likely to appear in the way Generation Z communicates.
2. TikTok trends significantly influence Generation Z’s communication culture, particularly in familiar and casual interactions. Respondents often use trends as tools for self-expression, relatability, and building personal connections.
3. The Generation Z perceive that a communication barrier between Generation may exist, mostly due to older generations’ unfamiliarity with digital trends. Despite these differences, Gen Z still uses TikTok expressions as a natural part of their identity and self-expression. Though this sometimes causes a subtle disconnect, it rarely leads to direct conflict.
4. Generation Z generally understands the importance of maintaining professional tones in formal written and verbal contexts, especially when communicating with authority figures. However, the use of TikTok-related expressions can still appear in formal environments, but only when Gen Z finds it appropriate, useful, or engaging for the situation.
5. Collaborative efforts, such as forums and workshops, by Generation Z and the older generations may foster better understanding of each other’s communication cultures. Furthermore, proposed academic interventions may help students learn to communicate

appropriately in academic settings while still expressing their individuality, and may also assist faculty in adapting their teaching styles to connect more effectively with their students.

Recommendations

1. The academe is recommended adapt Digital Literacy and Etiquette courses or seminars to enrich awareness and education about maneuvering this emerging digital landscape and adjusting teaching strategies based on the dynamic communication culture of younger generations.
2. Parents and guardians should have an open dialogue and communication in order to create an environment where digital responsibilities are practiced and media exposure is filtered.
3. Future researchers are recommended to delve into whether there is a pattern of communication culture evolution between generations, expound the culture comparisons between these generations to add variations to identify unique native implications, and expand the number of respondents to discover more significantly accurate implications and findings.

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